

Digital transformation and its role in improving the quality of health services in Algeria

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to highlight the significant role brought about by digital transformation in public administrations in Algeria, especially in the healthcare sector. It has contributed to improving the performance of hospital institutions and enhancing the quality of healthcare services. Through this study, we also addressed the challenges facing this digital transformation. The study's findings summarized that the healthcare system in Algeria has experienced some advancements in light of digital transformation, particularly after the COVID-19 pandemic, which exposed gaps in healthcare services, necessitating the inclusion of digital transformation in various healthcare institutions. This is what we will attempt to analyze in this research paper by examining the key events and developments in the healthcare sector under the influence of digital transformation.

Key words: Digital Transformation; Healthcare Sector; COVID-19 pandemic; Algeria.

المخلص:

تهدف هذه الدراسة الى إبراز الدور المهم الذي أحدثته التحول الرقمي على الإدارات العمومية في الجزائر وخاصة على قطاع الصحة، حيث ساهم في تحسين اداءات المؤسسات الاستشفائية وتحسين جودة الخدمات الصحية، ومن خلال هذه الدراسة تطرقنا أيضا إلى التحديات التي تواجه هذا التحول الرقمي. وتلخصت نتائج الدراسة إلى أن المنظومة الصحية في الجزائر عرفت بعض التطورات في ظل التحول الرقمي، وخاصة بعد جائحة كوفيد-19 الذي أظهرت الفجوات في الخدمات الصحية مما ساهم بضرورة شمول التحول الرقمي في شتى المؤسسات الصحية، وذلك ما سنحاول تحليله في هذه الورقة البحثية بالوقوف على أهم الأحداث والتطورات في قطاع الصحة في ظل التحول الرقمي.

الكلمات المفتاحية: التحول الرقمي؛ قطاع الصحة؛ جائحة كوفيد-19؛ الجزائر.

Introduction:

E-government is considered the optimal method of utilizing electronic and computer technologies. Its main goal is to reduce paper usage and wasted space by converting important documents and files into electronic formats. This strategy has become necessary across various sectors, such as the healthcare sector. It is undeniable that information and communication technologies (ICT) have become powerful drivers relied upon for the success of social and economic development programs, whether regionally or nationally and across all sectors. Based on this, Algeria has embraced ICT and the resulting digital transformation of Algerian society. The objective is to build a comprehensive information society and elevate the country to a knowledge-based economy. This research paper aims to provide an analytical overview of the current state of digital transformation in the healthcare administration sector. It explores the advantages, obstacles, and challenges associated with this transformation.

Problem Statement:

To what extent has digital transformation contributed to improving the quality of healthcare services in Algeria?

Significance of the Study:

The topic of digital transformation is highly significant, especially given recent technological advancements and the rapid global events, necessitating the modernization of public administrations across all sectors. This is aimed at facilitating services and increasing productivity by saving time and resources.

Study Objectives:

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Understand the key stages of development in the healthcare sector in Algeria.
- Modernize the healthcare sector in the context of digital transformation.
- Identify the challenges and prospects arising from this transformation.

Study Methodology:

To achieve the study's objectives, a descriptive-analytical methodology will be employed to understand the role of digital transformation in enhancing the quality of healthcare services in Algeria. This will involve analyzing relevant statistical tables.

Study Structure:

To address the problem statement, the study is divided into three main axes:

1. Digital transformation.
2. The healthcare sector in Algeria.
3. The contribution of digital transformation to improving the quality of healthcare services.
4. Challenges and prospects.

First: Digital Transformation

1- Digital transformation definition

Digital transformation is considered one of the most studied phenomena in information systems and the literature of organizational sciences, especially with the emergence of new digital technologies at an increasing pace. The terms digitization or digital transformation hold various meanings, where digitization is defined as the method through which many areas of social life are restructured around digital communications and the underlying structure of media. On the other hand, digital transformation is a process aimed at enhancing an entity by implementing significant changes to its characteristics through a set of information, computing, communication, and networking technologies¹.

Furthermore, digital transformation is known as a new business model that relies on utilizing modern mechanisms and technologies to innovate new products and services, reshape their distribution, and orient them towards the user.

1-1 the concept of digital health

Figure 01: Digital Health Terms

Source: Prepared by researchers

The use of health information technology in healthcare and the utilization of information and communication technology for health purposes represent two distinct definitions, given that the concept of health is broader than that of healthcare. For example, improving a patient's health condition differs from enhancing their clinical status².

Digital health or electronic health is a term used to encompass a wide range of technologies employed in healthcare, including health informatics, health education, and health promotion. This term has been recently defined by the World Health Organization, especially in response to the spread of COVID-19, as follows: "Digital health is the use of digital technologies (such as mobile phones) for health, often combined with the use of emerging fields such as advanced analytics, artificial intelligence, and genomics."³.

Building upon the aforementioned concepts, digital health encompasses the realm of knowledge and practices associated with the development and use of digital technologies to

improve health and cater to the digital consumer through various smart tools, media, and emerging technologies that support healthcare services. This approach moves towards decentralization in healthcare, relieving burden from hospitals and clinics, in alignment with the fundamental principles laid out by the World Health Organization:

1. Meeting individuals' health needs through comprehensive care, including guidance, prevention, and treatment throughout their lifespan.
2. Addressing broader health determinants (including social, economic, and environmental factors, as well as individual characteristics and behaviors) through evidence-based policies and procedures across all sectors.
3. Empowering individuals, families, and local communities to optimize their health, as advocates for policies that promote and protect health and well-being, as contributors to the development of healthcare and social services, and as caregivers for themselves and others.

1-2 and importance of e-governance

- Foundations of E-Government: E-Government is built upon several foundational principles, in Diversified Communication Channels: This leads to service diversity for citizens and beneficiaries of institutions through multiple service delivery channels.
- Administrative Responsibility and Transparency: Enhances the effectiveness of administrative information and procedures by promoting transparency.
- Utilization of Electronic Methods: Ensures that all service recipients access services and information through electronic devices.
- Electronic Security Availability, especially for sensitive information.
- Quality Factor Availability: Necessitates a review of communication policies, information systems, administrative units, and their relationships.
- Accessibility Ease: Guarantees citizens' access to services and information through electronic devices.
- Collaboration Among Public Administrations: Enables interaction between departments and the provision of joint services for citizens. Mutual recognition of electronic documents and identity verification systems.
- Technological Neutrality: Progress in using open standards or those widely used by the public, avoiding reliance on software tools with licensing costs in citizen interactions ⁴.

1-3 the importance of digitization in the health sector

Healthcare contributes to approximately 10.4% of the global GDP, with the value of electronic health exports reaching around \$80 billion in 2017. Digital health relies on artificial intelligence, big data, electronic health records, and remote healthcare. Therefore, we can summarize its advantages as follows:

1. Improved quality of healthcare services.
2. Reduced costs and increased resource planning efficiency.
3. Enhanced database and evidence base for timely use.
4. Monitoring and geographical/demographic containment of epidemics, as seen with COVID-19.
5. More accurate diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment of patients.
6. Providing better, personalized, and tailored services.

Fagherazzi⁵ emphasized the importance of telemedicine and the use of social media to reduce the risk of infection transmission. Kapoor highlighted the role of digital solutions in combating epidemics like the coronavirus, considering them the best available solutions worldwide. Van Spall provided a vision for leveraging digital technology to manage and contain epidemics through proactive monitoring, expanded testing, and restricted isolation of the infected, a vision that researchers have found successful in some advanced countries.

2- Quality of health services under digitization

2-1 Quality of Health Services

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines healthcare quality as "conformance to standards and proper performance in a safe and socially acceptable manner, at an affordable cost, leading to a significant impact on disease rates, mortality rates, disabilities, and malnutrition." The Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations in the United States defines it as "the degree of compliance with recognized standards for determining a good level of practice and knowing the expected outcomes of a specific medical service, procedure, diagnosis, or treatment." From these two definitions, it is evident that quality is determined based on adherence to professional standards and is measured retrospectively using predefined criteria with the goal of improvement and continuous development.

Therefore, healthcare service quality can be defined as "the continuous pursuit of meeting patient requirements at the lowest possible cost, encompassing three key points: firstly, achieving quality from the patient's perspective; secondly, achieving quality from a professional perspective, which involves providing the best services according to the latest scientific and professional methods; and thirdly, focusing on quality from an administrative perspective, primarily concerning how available resources are utilized and the ability to attract additional resources to meet the necessary needs for providing exceptional service."

2-2 Health Service Quality Goals

Healthcare quality encompasses many tangible objectives that healthcare institutions aim to achieve, including⁶:

- Understanding patient opinions and measuring their satisfaction levels regarding healthcare services, especially in terms of healthcare planning, goal setting, and related policies.
- Ensuring the mental and physical well-being of stakeholders.
- Providing high-quality healthcare services that lead to the satisfaction of beneficiaries, as this is the primary goal of quality implementation.
- Earning the satisfaction of beneficiaries, thereby improving performance and gaining their approval.
- Enhancing the morale of healthcare professionals and building their trust to achieve the best goals and outcomes.
- Ensuring the physical and mental health of beneficiaries.

It is clear from the previous two definitions that quality is determined on the basis of adherence to professional standards and measured retroactively using the established criteria

2-3 dimensions of health service quality

Any definition of healthcare service quality must align with several dimensions. These dimensions serve as a framework that helps healthcare providers identify and analyze problems and measure performance against agreed-upon standards. There is no consensus among researchers on the dimensions that define the level of service quality. However, healthcare quality generally has two fundamental dimensions:

1. **Tangible Quality:** This is the quality that the client experiences when receiving the service. It includes the physical and tangible aspects of the service.
2. **Interactive Quality:** This represents the performance of the service during the interaction between staff and clients within the institution.

Researchers have also identified two additional dimensions of healthcare quality:

3. **Technical Quality:** This refers to the actual outputs of the service, indicating how well a specific healthcare problem is addressed.
4. **Functional Quality:** This concerns the relationships and interactions between the client and the service provider.

These dimensions of quality can be grouped into three categories:

- **Technical Dimension:** This involves the application of knowledge and technology to a specific healthcare issue.
- **Non-Technical Dimension:** This encompasses the psychological and social interaction between the service provider and the individual receiving the service.
- **Physical Facilities Dimension:** This relates to the place where the service is delivered, including the ease of service provision, the general condition of the facilities, the appearance of staff, and the modernity of equipment.

Some researchers have further distilled these dimensions into five key dimensions that determine service quality based on client perception ⁷:

1. **Reliability:** The ability to deliver the service accurately and on time, meeting commitments. This dimension represents 32% of the relative importance in quality compared to other dimensions.
2. **Responsiveness:** The ability to handle complaints and suggestions effectively and to provide the service with an open attitude. This dimension represents 22% of the relative importance in quality.

3. **Assurance:** The assurance that the service is free from error, danger, or doubt, including both psychological and material aspects. This dimension represents 19% of the relative importance in quality.
4. **Empathy:** Demonstrating a friendly, caring attitude towards the client and recognizing their importance and the desire to meet their needs. This dimension represents 16% of the relative importance in quality.
5. **Tangibles:** Concerns the tangible aspects related to service delivery, including equipment, facility conditions, staff appearance, and the modernity of equipment. This dimension represents 16% of the relative importance in quality.

3- The Impact of Digitization on Healthcare Services within the Healthcare Institution

Healthcare institutions have not reached this level of progress except as a result of historical developments that have occurred over the ages, starting from ancient civilizations and continuing into the modern era. Consequently, we can distinguish between three fundamental stages in the evolution of the healthcare institution:

- The healthcare institution in ancient civilizations.
- The healthcare institution in the Islamic era.
- The healthcare institution in the modern era.

3-1 the reality of the digitization of Algeria's health sector

Algeria, like many other countries around the world, is facing a significant crisis in the level of healthcare services. It is in dire need of continuous efforts to improve these services and create more effective and efficient healthcare institutions. This highlights the relationship between the human and economic aspects that define the dimensions of hospitals as public service institutions in Algeria, subject to governmental supervision and reliant on partial free healthcare.

Like other organizations, hospitals in Algeria urgently need to keep pace with current developments to enhance the quality of healthcare services they provide. It's worth noting that electronic management has begun to make its way into Algerian hospitals, albeit at a slow pace. The primary objectives are cost-effectiveness, quality care, and service rationalization.

While most modern hospitals resort to electronic management to provide necessary primary care services, promote individual and community health, educate and train medical and nursing

personnel, activating electronic management in Algerian hospitals to achieve their healthcare functions efficiently and effectively still faces numerous obstacles, including⁸:

- Insufficient political administration.
- Poor healthcare institution management.
- Low healthcare service quality.
- Resistance to digitization.
- Inadequate training of personnel to meet the challenges of electronic management.
- Bureaucracy and project shortages.

In the contemporary context, electronic management in Algerian hospitals represents a necessary organizational, administrative, and legal inevitability to enable the state to fulfill its functions in maintaining the health of individuals and the community effectively. Only through effective and modern electronic management in its policies, organization, human resources, material resources, technical resources, legal resources, scientific resources, and technological resources can Algeria overcome the current and future healthcare service shortcomings. This can be achieved by:

- Transitioning to electronic management for patient files, which is currently underway in some hospitals to facilitate communication, scheduling, and care, and to enhance trust with citizens.
- Strengthening internal and external communication networks to save time, enhance efficiency, and manage healthcare services and expenses as well as various regulatory activities.
- Providing adequate training for staff and medical teams to align with the requirements of electronic management.
- Promoting a culture of transitioning to electronic management.
- It's essential to recognize that digitizing information content in institutions, especially healthcare, brings numerous benefits, including:

- Expanding the database related to various departments in healthcare institutions, supporting the work of senior management and providing them with appropriate information for managing their work in different departments.
- Enhancing opportunities for performance development in various departments.
- Facilitating document retrieval and search, ensuring quick access and availability to multiple individuals simultaneously in the same location.
- Rationalizing storage locations and archives, particularly related to paper documents, with the capacity to hold large quantities of digital documents such as patient records.

Moreover, digitization promotes the principle of equality in service provision to all individuals without bias, preventing favoritism and allowing for the establishment of positive principles that improve the quality of services provided through the design of policies and strategies for electronic management. Therefore, all departments in healthcare institutions must be compelled to use electronic methods to improve their performance and move away from traditional approaches. Continuously enhancing the administrative infrastructure to align with modern technological developments is essential.

It is also necessary to monitor and intensify studies in the field of electronic management and understand its actual impact on the development and improvement of services, especially in healthcare in Algeria. Electronic management has become an opportunity to overcome many administrative problems in healthcare organizations.

3-2 Impact of Health Sector Digitization on Health Services

Health institutions, like other service-oriented organizations, always strive to provide better services to citizens by keeping up with technological advancements⁹. They have directed their efforts towards digitizing their processes and offering a multitude of services electronically. This has contributed to the improvement of their services.

The impacts of digitization on healthcare services are as follows:

1. **Aspects of Impact:** The effects of implementing digitization in various aspects of healthcare services include:
 - **Ease of Access:** The primary goal is to ensure citizens' access to healthcare services at any time and from any location, especially for patients in isolated areas and small villages. This is achieved by eliminating the need for patients to travel long distances to hospitals.

- **Cost Reduction:** A significant challenge in modern healthcare is the persistent increase in costs, which may not be acceptable for both economically deprived and affluent regions. Information technology and communication, through remote monitoring and telehealthcare, help in cost reduction.
- **Service Quality:** Information technology and communication tools provided, such as devices and equipment, contribute to improving the quality of healthcare service.

3-3 - Advantages of applying digitization to healthcare

The advantages of implementing digitization benefit doctors, patients, healthcare workers, and citizens in general. Some prominent advantages include:

- **Data Accumulation:** Healthcare institutions amass vast amounts of data, utilizing big data, artificial intelligence, and Internet of Things (IoT) technology for enhanced utilization. Data collection and analysis lead to improved diagnosis and treatment. Institutions can gather patient-related data and facilitate diagnosis through various methods, including:
- **Cloud Systems:** Cloud systems enable data sharing, easy search, retrieval, and interoperability among medical systems, IoT devices, and applications.
- **AI in Medical Imaging:** Artificial intelligence is employed for analyzing medical images and electronic health records to aid in diagnosis.
- **Big Data Analysis:** Leveraging big data analysis to monitor public health records, social media, and other data sources to identify insights relevant to healthcare institutions, such as disease outbreak reports and complaints, and to review healthcare services ¹⁰.
- **Efficiency and Effectiveness:** Enhancing work efficiency and effectiveness.
- **Improved Communication:** Enhancing communication among stakeholders in healthcare services.
- **Reducing Distances:** Bridging geographical gaps.
- **Enhanced Information and Knowledge Sharing:** Facilitating improved sharing of information and knowledge.
- **Enhanced Decision-Making:** Improving decision-making processes.

- **Time-Efficiency:** Reducing wastage of time.
- **Cost Reduction:** Reducing costs.
- **Medical Error Reduction:** Decreasing medical errors.
- **Avoiding Information Redundancy:** Reducing duplicated information.
- **Enhanced Medical Research and Statistical Processes:** Improving medical research and statistical operations.

These advancements aim to contribute to the overall improvement of healthcare quality, accessibility, and efficiency.

4- Challenges to digital transformation in the health sector

The development of any system in a sector faces significant challenges that can hinder its success. Some of these challenges include:

- **Data Management:** Processing and analysing data is a major challenge in the healthcare field. Part of the problem is the enormous amount of data continuously collected by hospitals, clinics, and specialists. Real-time processing becomes difficult, and without an artificial intelligence model capable of analysing this data, institutions find it challenging to provide better personalized healthcare ¹¹.
- **Data Privacy:** With the healthcare industry shifting towards collaborative healthcare concepts, there are increasing risks of patient data exposure. This is because data and information are often accessible across complex medical environments, making them available to many users through various devices and locations.
- **Cybersecurity:** Data breaches related to data hacking pose a significant threat to society¹². Cybersecurity is a major concern in the digital transformation of healthcare. A single malicious software attack can breach a patient's private data and cause harm. This not only disrupts patient care but can also damage the reputation of healthcare organizations.
- **Initial Costs:** Digital transformation in healthcare requires a substantial investment in technology. Healthcare organizations primarily focus on costs and returns first, with the use of technological tools often coming later.
- **Skill Shortages:** Digital transformation in healthcare requires patients and healthcare professionals to use new tools and technologies. Digital technologies offer multiple solutions to patients or healthcare workers, emphasizing the importance of digital

technology and its integration into the healthcare sector¹³. However, not everyone possesses technological literacy, and teaching people these new skills can also be a challenge.

- **Compliance with Healthcare Regulations:** Healthcare regulations are essential for protecting medical records and patient personal information at any cost. Compliance with these regulations is essential for the long-term success of your healthcare digitization.

5- Conclusion:

Considering the importance of digital transformation and modernizing administrations, we have attempted in this research paper to analyze the reality of digitization in the healthcare sector in Algeria and the challenges it faces. The Algerian healthcare system faces many challenges, and the proliferation of diseases necessitates the need for modern healthcare requirements to cover all deficiencies in terms of human resources, equipment, and financing. We observed this during the COVID-19 pandemic, which revealed numerical gaps in the healthcare sector, similar to various other sectors. Hence, the need to increase the use of digitization in healthcare and introduce new projects in this sector, such as the previously mentioned electronic services, which are of great importance in the healthcare sector. In addition to numerous digital services planned to be added in administrations to relieve the pressure on hospitals and facilitate administrative procedures for patients and management.

With digital transformation, the government aims to utilize this technological advancement for its benefit, invest in this field, and develop the national economy. This requires joint efforts from the administration to provide facilities and address challenges, especially internet issues, as this last factor will not succeed without the readiness of internet services, human resource training, and citizens' acceptance of digital administration, keeping up with the events that bring benefits to all aspects of healthcare in Algeria and contribute to the overall improvement of the sector's quality and efficiency from all perspectives and, consequently, the public benefit of the sector and the country.

6- Proposals and Recommendations:

Through our study, we have come up with some proposals and recommendations, including:

- Embracing technological advancement in various administrations while addressing the challenges.

- Raising awareness among citizens about the importance of learning modern technologies and using applications effectively.
- Not neglecting institutions in remote areas and ensuring the universalization of services.
- Considering the elderly population and illiterate individuals who may not be familiar with modern technologies.
- Most importantly, rigorous monitoring of keeping pace with modernization and periodically converting paper files to digital, as daily digital information digitization, especially statistical data, is a very important point for foresight studies by researchers to analyze phenomena, improve services, identify gaps, and address them by experts in the field.

This will ultimately contribute to the advancement of healthcare services in Algeria and benefit the nation as a whole.

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